

On the Fluorination of Organic Compounds. Part II.

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In continuation of our work (Rây, Goswami and Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 93) we have attempted to prepare organic fluo-compounds by the action of thalious fluoride on aliphatic and aromatic compounds containing a reactive halogen atom. By following this method we have obtained methyl and ethyl fluoacetates as also benzyl fluoride. In other cases, either the products could not be isolated in pure condition or the reaction products decomposed. Thalious fluoride did not, however, react with α -bromoacetoacetic ester, α -bromopropionic ester, α -bromocinnamic acid, bromocyclohexane, chloroacetanide, iodoacetaldehyde, biomocamphor, *m*-bromonitrobenzene, under the experimental conditions described below. Hence this method of fluorination is not of so wide an applicability as was supposed by us. The above three fluo-compounds had the properties ascribed to them by Swarts (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1896, *iii*, 15, 1134) and by Ingold and Ingold (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2249). Our method for the preparation of benzyl fluoride is easier than that of Ingold and Ingold. The yield is also better.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Methyl Fluoacetate.—Methyl bromoacetate (16 g.), anhydrous thalious fluoride (24 g.) and absolute alcohol were refluxed together for 36 hours. The reaction mixture was then filtered and the filtrate was kept in contact with anhydrous calcium chloride. The liquid was then fractionated. On redistillation, methyl fluoacetate was obtained as a colourless liquid, slightly lachrymatory, soluble in water, b.p. 104°. (Found : F, 20.00. Calc. for $C_3H_5O_2F$: F, 20.65 per cent).

Ethyl Fluoacetate.—Ethyl bromoacetate (24 g.), anhydrous thalious fluoride (40 g.) and absolute alcohol were refluxed together for 24 hours. The filtrate from the reaction mixture was fractionated, when a colourless liquid, b. p. 126°, was obtained. (Found : F, 17.1. Calc. for $C_4H_7O_2F$: F, 17.9 per cent).

Benzyl Fluoride.—An alcoholic solution of benzyl bromide (18g.) was refluxed with anhydrous thallous fluoride (30 g.) for 32 hours. The filtrate of the reaction product was freed from alcohol on the water-bath and the residue distilled, when a light yellow viscous distillate was obtained, b.p. 140°. It is lachrymatory and decomposes slowly evolving hydrofluoric acid (Found : F, 17.00. Calc. for C_7H_7F : F, 17.27 per cent).

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Variation of Cataphoretic Velocity of Colloidal Particles during Aggregation. Part II.

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In a recent paper (Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Bhabak, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 370) it has been shown that for a number of colloids and electrolytes

(i) the cataphoretic velocity increases with time with progressing aggregation of the colloidal particles at a constant concentration of the added electrolyte;

(ii) the increase in c. v. with time is often more marked, the higher the valency of the precipitating ions;

(iii) the c. v. of the supernatant suspension of a colloid after partial coagulation is less than that of the colloid before coagulation;

(iiii) the c. v. of the coagula of a sol (As_2S_3) is the same as that of the supernatant suspension of the colloid after coagulation.

These results are contradictory to the existing theories (Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Bhabak, *loc. cit.*), which lay the main stress on the thickness and the capacity of the double layer, on the radius of the particle and on the ionic strength of the medium and neglect the changes in the distribution of ions on aggregation which appear to be more important than the factors just mentioned. An explanation on this basis has been put forward by Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Ghosh (*Trans. National Inst. Sci. India*, 1936, 1, 47-82) and by Mukherjee,